

NECESSITY OF TEACHING THE SCIENCE OF "SAFETY OF LIFE ACTIVITIES" IN THE CONDITIONS OF INNOVATIVE EDUCATION

Makhmudov Sodir Yusufalievich

Intern researcher at Fergana Polytechnic Institute

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Abstract. *In this article, technologies are developing and penetrating into all spheres of society and production, new types of dangers for humans are increasing in the period when human manual labor is increasingly being replaced by mental work and artificial intelligence, and the importance of the science of life activity in preventing them. ideas about tasks are given.*

Keywords: *safety, life activity, technology, human, nature, danger, event.*

In the context of innovative education, within the framework of programs of training specialists created on the basis of international standards, the subject “safety of life activities” is included in the main subjects, and creative technologies for the development of this discipline are being applied to the educational process. Prior to 2030, the concept of Education, adopted by international organizations and developed countries, was recognized as “the main driving force of Education and development and an important activity that sustainable development brings to the goals.” In the conditions of innovative education, systematic work is being carried out on the implementation of creative directions of training of competitive personnel, variative forms of training, mechanisms for the development of the subject “safety of life activity” in future specialists.

In the further improvement of the educational process, it is of great importance to reform the content of education, to coordinate it with world educational standards. In this sense, the choice of the content and structural structure of education is a complex issue of practical importance. Here we want to proceed from the essence of the educational process, noting the importance of the structural structure of science in the assimilation of the methodological foundations of science, common to students in the teaching of science in the educational process. At the same time, the content of science for students, taking into account the peculiarity of science, should form a logical structural structure aimed at students being able to perfect their scientific worldview, scientifically analyze evidence, educate independent thinking, thinking skills, master the skills of their practical use. The student's worldview is that without his mere attitude to objective reality, it is his place in society, his attitude to socio-political life, his understanding of the essence of the laws of nature, his ability to put them into practice.

Improving the content of curricula and textbooks in education, in particular, determining its structural structure in new content, revising the way in which educational materials are arranged according to the purpose of each section and topics, are the main factors of the educational and educational process. The focus of the science of safety of life activity is the role of man in the development of society. Life activity safety is human activity in all conditions. All active movement of a person constitutes his activity. The science of safety of life activities covered the Departments of Environmental Communication of human activities, safety in labor activities and safety in emergency situations, fire safety and sanitary hygiene. The safety of life activities is a

science based on principles and methods: that puts and addresses on a large scale issues of reducing accidents, victims and the damage they cause.

Life activity security is the theoretical basis of security that can be applied in any browsing activity. Life is full of danger. Not being able to assess it correctly can have very bad consequences. Currently, a person lives and works in a world of natural, technical, economic and various other dangers. As a result of these dangers, too many people become disabled, become ill, and lose their lives. From such dangers, the science of “safety of life activities” teaches the protection of society, personality and state.

The science of life activity safety – studies the general dangers that threaten each person and the various means of protection of a person from them in different life circumstances. The science of safety of life activity is a set of technical, sanitary and hygienic and legal measures aimed at ensuring safe working conditions for a person and his health.

This science does not solve special security problems. It is a scientific and methodological science and serves as the basis for the special Sciences of security. Many great allomas have been involved in the issues of safety of life activities since ancient times. For Example, Hippocrates, Aristotle, Agricola, M.V.Lomonosov, Kirpichev V.L., The nikolskys were also concerned with the security problem. The great Uzbek judge Abu Ali ibn Sino founded the discipline of hygiene with his work. Academic V. development of the problem of safety in the development of the Technosphere.A.Legasov dedicated his scientific work.

The purpose and main function of the science of safety of life activities is to conduct economic issues closely related to the protection of the environment. The tasks of science include:

1. Labor activity safety requirement legal literacy training;
2. Providing guidance and preparation of guidelines for the safety of Mehat activities;
3. Study of the concepts of the employment contract and the principles of labor protection in it;
4. Preparation of a specialist from the theoretical and practical side of the study of the processes of interaction of the activity of the body with the conditions of production.

Tasks of life Activity Safety Science

When a logical structural structure of a teaching material is said, it is usually understood that the internal connections of concepts and thought-patterns in the learning disciplines and their

influence on each other, dictate each other. The science of life activity safety is organized on the basis of the science of labor protection, atrophyte protection and civil protection. The science of life activity safety studies the types of dangers that threaten a person and the means by which a person is protected from them in different life circumstances.

Danger is the central concept of the safety of vital activity, understood as those that do not harm the health of a person directly or in other ways, that is, the creators of unforeseen phenomena, consequences. Risks will be hidden and real. There must be clear conditions for the implementation of hidden risks. These conditions are called causation. We can express the issues that the science of life activity safety considers through the following scheme.

The growth of modern science and technology, the introduction of new technology and machine-mechanisms presupposes that every employee working in production is highly qualified, understands and adheres to the laws of technology.

At present, there are no conditions that ensure the complete disappearance of accidents in industrial enterprises, regardless of how many recommendations, regulations and criteria are developed for ensuring the safety of workers. Failure to comply with safety techniques, industrial sanitation, and fire safety regulations, and may result in injuries to workers, poisoning, and occupational diseases in industrial enterprises. Therefore, any accident that occurs at production enterprises is comprehensively checked and taken into account.

Educational material is a complex of knowledge that must be mastered, formed in a certain way. In the educational process as a whole, educational material occupies a central place. In this sense, the question of the logical structure of educational material is of great importance in the educational process. Therefore, the structural structure (structure) of science is considered important for each discipline. In many cases, the concept of structure is interpreted as the gain or decrease of the structural fragments of the whole, or in the sense of influencing the essence of the system by placing its parts in what order, merging into one whole or, conversely, decomposing, sometimes adding an element to the whole or separating them from the whole.

A system with a structure forms a completed whole. The parts of the whole-the elements are seriously interconnected, and in the form of the arrangement of the elements, the rigidity of a certain order, the structure is manifested as a result of their interaction. thus, a structure is a strict, stationary correspondence of interacting elements in one whole system. Therefore, the educational

material has a certain structure, which is determined on the basis of the structure and content of the educational subject.

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